

Operational Storage: Think short and long term

[Evaluate & Archive](#)

Assess Data Retention

Determine what data must be retained or destroyed for contractual, legal, or regulatory purposes, and how long the data will be retained and preserved. Additionally, data and related records might be identified for permanent storage as a part of the historical record of a discipline or institution, or as intellectual property.

- **[Harvard Research Records Retention](#)**: Researchers have certain obligations to record, maintain and retain research records, and to make those records available for grant monitoring and auditing purposes. In general, essential research records should be retained for a period of no fewer than seven (7) years after the end of a research project or activity.
- **[Essential Research Records](#)**:
 - substantiating grant applications or demonstrating compliance with contractual terms
 - substantiating published research and patents, whether the research is sponsored or not
 - substantiating research described in grant proposals and other funding requests
 - records considered for permanent preservation and access by the Archives and Records Management Program at the Center for the History of Medicine

Appraise Data for Archiving

A small percentage of data and related records may be identified for permanent storage as a part of the historical record of a discipline, institution, or as intellectual property. Harvard takes on all costs and security for archived data and records after appraisal and acquisition.

- **Records eligible for permanent retention maybe those that:**
 - document a breakthrough
 - are generated by a lab or individual who had a great impact on the field
 - are highly reusable in a particular area of research

★ ***Understand the difference between [“archiving”](#) and [“long-term storage”](#)***

Permanent retention or archiving is the ongoing migration of electronic formats and storage costs, as well as care, maintenance, and access services for the records in perpetuity. Long-term storage and preservation seek to ensure data will be available in a persistent and accessible format for the specific period outlined by your funder and institution.

Appropriately Dispose Data

Once the research has concluded, determine which data and records are safe to dispose of, including how you will permanently remove sensitive data or project data.

- [Retention & Maintenance of Research Records & Data Frequently Asked Questions \(FAQ\)](#): Guides the retention and maintenance of research records by Harvard faculty and staff.
- [General Records Schedule \(GRS\) and Research Records](#): Details how long to retain different types of records and whether to send records to an archive or destroy them when they are no longer required.
- [In-Office Destruction Documentation Form](#): Used to document in-office destruction of records whose retention period has expired.

★ **Consult the Center for the History of Medicine [Archives and Records Management Program](#)**

The ARM program can assist you with appraising your research for long-term historical value, and help managing and disposing of data or records associated with your research.